

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B345
Date: 16 February 2008
Take Off: 18:01:52Z 01:42:56Z
Landing: 23:17:37Z 03:17:51Z
Flight Time 5h 15m 45 1h 34m 55

Campaign: CLPX II

Operating Area: Barrow, Alaska

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM Trainer	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
4	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chem / AVAPS /CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
8	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
9	CVI / Nephelometers	Rob King	Met Office
10	DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office
11	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 1	Jon Taylor	Met Office
13	Mission Scientist 2	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	Dave Kindred	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 4	Richard Essary	University of Edinburgh

Flight Track:

B345 Track 17-FEB-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B345
 Date: 16 Jan 2008
 Project: CLPX II
 Location: Barrow, Alaska

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
165621		Hangar Posn	0.47 kft	345	64'49.60N, 147' 51.03
175053		Pan Posn	0.49 kft	221	64'49.60N, 147'51.00W
1752		Video	0.48 kft	221	Start FFC
175326		ASP	0.48 kft	221	Open
180152		T/O	2.0 kft	047	Fairbanks
181312		Video	19.2 kft	317	FFC & DFC
184729	191502	Profile 1	24.1 - 1.1 kft	337	Down to 1k', QNH 29.83
191503	195009	Run 1.1	1.1 kft	349	A-B at 1k'
192515		Video	1.1 kft	349	Start FFC & DFC 2
192932		Event	1.1 kft	348	Coast out
193905		Event	1.1 kft	346	Ice transition
195042		Event	1.1 kft	055	Heimann cal
195153	200709	Run 1.2	1.1 kft	215	B-C, 1k' Over Ice Stn
202014	203059	Profile 2	1.1 - 12.1 kft	045	1k' - 12k' on Q29.83
203220	204748	Profile 2	12.1 - 27.0 kft	162	From 12k'
204937	210233	Profile 2	27.0 - 34.0 kft	326	300fpm at end
205438		Event	31.6 kft	335	Reduce climb rate
205812		Video	32.8 kft	354	Start FFC & DFC3
205843		Event	33.0 kft	353	Zero Nev TWC
210526	212801	Run 2.1	34.0 kft	184	
210901		Sonde	34.0 kft	184	Launch #01
211400		Sonde	34.0 kft	184	Launch #02
211701		Sonde	34.0 kft	185	Launch #03
211900		Event			IASI Overpass
212300		Sonde	34.0 kft	184	Launch #04
212601		Sonde	34.0 kft	190	Launch #05
213355	215408	Run 2.2	34.0 kft	344	To -B
213600		Sonde	34.0 kft	331	Launch #06
214002		Sonde	34.0 kft	334	Launch #07
214017		Event	34.0 kft	334	Contrailing
214300		Sonde	34.0 kft	333	Launch #08
215636	222625	Profile 3	34.0 - 1.1 kft	175	B-A, 1000 fpm 1k'
222748	225755	Run 3.1	1.1 kft	349	A- short of B, 1k' ,Q29.87
223114		Video	1.1 kft	351	Start FFC & DFC4
224214		Event	1.1 kft	351	Coast out
224539		Event	1.1 kft	349	Transition
224550		Event	1.1 kft	349	Heimann Cal
225855	231031	Run 3.2	1.1 kft	237	near B-D, 1k'
231737		Land	0.10 kft	337	Barrow
232215		Videos	0.09 kft	273	Stop
232240		Shutdown	0.09 kft	273	71'17.21N, 156'46.71W
013451		Start-Up	0.12 kft	273	71'17.21N, 156'46.71W
013459		ASP	0.12 kft	273	Open
014256		T/O	0.63 kft	106	Barrow
014325	020825	Profile 4	1.1 - 25.0 kft	149	From the surface
015744		Event	15.2 kft	156	Bullet rosettes seen
024410		Video	25.1 kft	159	End of Tapes
031751		Land	0.74 kft	039	Fairbanks
032243		Shutdown	0.74 kft	226	64'49.60N,147'50.96W

B345 Track 17-FEB-08

SORTIE BRIEF

CLPX-II – Land and Sea Ice Surface Property Studies.

Flight B345
Date: 16th Feb 2008

Mission Scientist: J Taylor

Science Aims: To characterise the land/sea ice surface properties under an overpass of the IASI satellite at 2119Z. Also to overfly a sea ice monitoring site just north of Barrow.

Weather: Cloud free conditions at all levels.

Waypoints:

Alpha 70°N, 155°W
Bravo 71°58' N 155 W
Charlie 71°21'56''N 156°32'39''W
Delta 71°21'57''N 156°32'39''W

Sortie Details:

1. 1800Z (0900L) Take off and transit to arrive at ALPHA at 1000ft after profile descent in to area (90mins)
2. 1930Z (1030L) Straight and level run from ALPHA to BRAVO at 1000ft (30mins)
3. 2000Z (1100L) Straight and level run towards CHARLIE at 1000ft (15mins)
4. 2015Z (1115L) Procedure turn after passing CHARLIE and then back to DELTA at 1000ft (10mins)
5. 2025Z (1125L) After passing DELTA profile ascent at 1000ft/min to FL350 to be at point BRAVO (35mins)
6. 2100Z (1200L) Straight and level run from BRAVO to ALPHA dropping 4 sondes (20mins)
7. 2125Z (1225L) Straight and level run from ALPHA to BRAVO at high level dropping 4 sondes (20mins)
8. 2145Z (1245L) Profile descent from BRAVO to ALPHA at 1000ft/min (35mins)
9. 2220Z (1320L) Straight and level run from ALPHA to BRAVO at 1000ft (30mins)
10. 2250Z (1350L) Recover to Land at Barrow
11. 2305Z (1405L) Land at Barrow

Refuel and then transit home – preferably recording science data on profile out of Barrow.

CLPX-II - B345 16th February 2008. Mission Scientist Debrief.

The aim of the flight was to underfly IASI over sea ice and land snow in clear sky conditions and also to overfly a sea ice monitoring site just offshore from Barrow on the northern slopes of Alaska. Both aims of the sortie were fully met in what was an excellent flight with a range of unique scientific data.

On transit to the operating area from Fairbanks there was extensive wave cloud over the Brooks Range of mountains in central Alaska but this cleared nicely in the operating area. The sortie began with a profile descent from FL240 down to 1000ft AMSL to point A a point some 60nm SSE of Barrow. The profile descent passed through the wave cloud with definite wave structure observed in the vertical velocities. The cirrus cloud was aggregates with size ~200-250um.

A run at 1000ft was flown from point Alpha to Point Bravo. There were totally cloud free conditions at the start of this run. There was extensive snow cover as far as the eye could see with very little obvious structure at the Southern end of the run. As we progressed North we passed over a region where snow was lying on lakes and the IR instruments and microwave instruments saw different brightness temps associated with this. During this run SID-1 saw the odd ice crystal but concentrations were very low. Surface winds were fairly light. As we passed over the land to sea ice transition MARSS saw a significant increase in BT as did Heimann and ARIES. The ARIES spectra showed that the contrast between the local air temp as measured in the CO2 region and the window region BTs swapped sign with the surface being warmer than the air when over the sea ice. Significant structure was seen in SWS, ARIES and MARSS/Deimos when we flew over leads that were had re-frozen. Towards the northern end of the run we flew under arctic stratus clouds.

After reaching point Bravo at low level we turned to overfly the ice station near Barrow and overflew the coordinates of the site four times. Unfortunately we were not able to make visible contact with the surface site but we got good microwave radiometer data in the region which will make a useful intercomparison. Having finished the low level data we then conducted a profile ascent up to FL340 tracking backwards and forwards N-S in the operating area.

A series of two high level runs were then flown at FL340 with the IASI overpass occurring during the first high level run. Towards the northern end of this run (i.e. the start) some of the run was flown over arctic stratus over sea ice but we also got clear skies over sea ice and land which should make an excellent intercomparison with IASI. Eight dropsondes were launched during these high level runs. ARIES made good nadir measurements with the occasional zenith view.

Following the high level run a profile was flown from Bravo to Alpha down to 1000ft and the low level run from Alpha to Bravo flown again. The ground track was different on this run so we did not pass exactly along the same flight track. This was good in that it allowed us to overfly a large frozen lake covered in snow that all the radiometers detected as different to the other surfaces. Once again significant temp differences were observed over the sea ice. Some of the leads were liquid and sea smoke was observed. A final run over the sea ice station was made but once again we were not able to make visual contact with the instrumented site (which is very small).

A refuel was made at Barrow. This took some considerable time due to delays with the fuel bowser but it did allow everyone to take in the atmosphere and experience surface temperatures of -32deg C. A profile ascent was flown out of Barrow on the transit home. By this time the skies were overcast with cirrus which we penetrated on the climb out – rosettes and columns were prevalent.

Summary

An excellent flight which will prove useful in our studies of using IR and microwave satellite data over sea ice and snow. The weather conditions were excellent with a contrast of totally cloud free conditions and some regions of arctic stratus over ice which is one of the toughest challenges for remote sensing.

Mission Scientist's Log

sws= 192.168.101.196.

CPX-11

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.345** Date 16/2/08 Name Son Tarrar Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
180152					Take Off from FARRABANKS.
					In Tank some cloud @ F2200 → F2240
181854		F2240	315		8/8 cloud above T = -36.5 Td = -40.2
					wind 19m/s 24 deg.
182656		F2240	313	16°40N 150°36W	cloud above. 22/242° -36.86 -41.28.
183558					Increasing low level cloud over Boats range cloud clearing nicely above.
184729	P1	F2240	328	18°N 152°22W	40/6/8 above 7/8 below. cloud below seems to be oriented E→W → potentially wave cloud.
185005		F2200	338		In wave cloud. 200 → 250m on ZPC aggregates.
185209		F2200			Out of cloud still quite old blue
185830		F150			clear above & below.
190638		F1090			clear above & below horizon indistinct some patchy Ci but generally ok.
191236					PEASL ≈ 120/cc SPC records nothing on ZPC
191503	P2.1	100ft Above-AMSL			Stg Run 1 ends P1 P1 Alpha Fuel alt = 790ft clear above & below

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Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B.365** Date **16 FEB 08** Name **Jon Taylor** Page **2** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
191820	R1		349		1000ft on 1010 hPa. 780m radar clear above + below featureless snow field. wind km/s 219deg T = -21°C Td = -21.61°C
192619					SID ≈ 10 cts/sec. Passed over coast. MARS saw muted inc in B Temps
19					Edge of swept ice -
192635					still clear above + below. MARS Env Temp @ 1000m = 263K.
					Passing over several frozen leads over lead Hermann = -8 clearer = -26°C.
194402		1000ft on 1010 hPa			Under v the Arctic St. ≈ 920ft on radar
					ZDC seeing ≈ 800µm
194533					clear above again
194710					Under cloud again
195009	R1.1	1000ft			End of Run 1 at Pt Bravo.
195153	R1.2	1000ft.	223	71°56N 157° E/W	Stg Run 1-2 towards Pt CHARLIE T = -21 Td = -20.17.
195530					clear per MARS ↑.

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Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B.345** Date **16/2/08** Name **Son Tapper** Page **3** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
195812					20K seeing low cumy & small spherical drops size?
200046					1/2 low cloud? ≈ 23/ditre 800um aggregates.
200200					Onwards over more ^{re-} frozen leech.
200450					Back over sharp fast ice
202014	P2↑	1000ft	043		sketch P2 climb near barrow.
	4 passes over region of ground ice				
203059		1200ft		an 1010kPa	Inland P2
203220	P2↑	1200ft↑	165	71°56'N 156°48'W	Restart P2 Broken cloud below.
204748	P2↑	F270	180		Interrupt P2 now turn back towards BRAND
204937	P2↑	F270↑	328	70°56'N 156°42'W	Restart P2 towards BRAND T = -68°C wind 28/233
205628	P2↑	F2310↑	335		Entering stratosphere O ₃ = 122.7ppb.
210233	P2	F2360			End of P2
210526	R2-1	F2360	182		Start Run 2-1 from BRAND ^{towards} R2P11A. Broken cloud below clear above
210900	R2-1	F2360			D1 gone. clear skies below ARIES software hung 211009
211400	R2-1	F2360	184		D2 gone. clear skies below.
211700	R2-1	F2360	185		D3 gone. clear skies below.
211900	R2-1	F2360	184		D4 gone. clear below ARIES
212300	R2-1	F2360	184		D4 gone.
212600	R2-1	F2360	184		D5 gone.

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211900 (P2P11A)

952 564 9093
Den Kline

CLAX-11

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B.365** Date 16/FEB/08 Name SEN TAYLOR Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
212801	R2.1	F2360	180		End Run 2.1 at ALPHA.
					Slow turn
213355	R2.2	F2360	342	70N 152°56'W	Start of Run 2.2 boundary BRAVO.
213600	R2.2	F2360	332		D6 gone.
					still clear below.
214000	R2.2	F2360	334	70N 36 153 30 W	D7 gone
21411					over large frozen lake etc
214230					back over frozen land some continuity
214300	"	"			D8 gone
214315					over sea ice boundary. clear skies
					below. + above.
215607					Much less low level cloud now
					at next on end of run
215408	R2.2	F1360			End Run 2.2 at BRAVO
					Turn round to descend to ALPHA.
215836	P3	F2360	175	71°48'N 155°18'W	Start of P3 run ALPHA BRAVO A
221200	P3	15000ft on 1012 hPa	175		over land still good cloud prog
					conditions.
					is encroaching from South
221846	P3	7500ft	176	70°26'N 156°18'W	Just going under edge at 70°26'N
222625	P3	1000ft	368°		End of P3 at ALPHA.
222748	R3	10000ft	1012 hPa	70N 156°W	Start Run 3 to BRAVO - Gamma.
223057					clear above.
					the over sea ice. - could not see

usual transition but Bernier saw rapid increase in surf temp as we hit sea ice.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B345

Date: 16/02/08 **Operator:** KFT **DRS Time:** 17:45:00 **DAU1 Time:** N/A **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** N/A **Page 1 of 1**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
18:00																ONLY 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID1 fitted Heaters on	
18:03:55	140	0.06		0		0		0								FL030	
18:06:44	30	0.06		-		0		0								FL090 SID1 OUT OF SYNCH - RESTARTED	
18:13:51	22	0.12		100		68	275	875	275							FL2000	
18:25																2DP switched off – too cold/noisy	
18:47:29	2	0.07		1		0										FL240 START P1	
18:48:51	1	0.11		0		0										FL230	
18:50:00	14	0.58		2000		687	175								8	FL220	
18:51:00	28	0.46		800		46	375								8	FL210	
18:52:10	3	0.11		40		1	400								8	FL200	
18:53:18	11	0.55		300		139	225								8	FL190	
18:54:18	33	0.25		200		86	325								8	FL180	
18:57:20	11	0.09		0		0										FL150	
18:58:21	6	0.08		0		0										FL140	
18:59:31	21	0.07		0		0										FL130	
19:01:03	33	0.08		0		0										FL120	
19:02:00	30	0.08		1		0										FL110	
19:03:11	45	0.09		1		0										FL100	
19:04:14	17	0.07		0		0										FL090	
19:05:36	17	0.08		0		0										FL080	
19:06:42	26	0.09		0		0										FL070	
19:07:57	37	0.08		1		0										FL060	
19:09:00	35	0.09		0		0										FL050	
19:10:31	72	0.09		1		0										FL040	
19:12:10	106	0.10		8		0										FL030	
19:13:50	121	0.11		8		0										FL020	
19:15:01	150	0.10		9		0										FL010 START R1 1000FT AGL	
19:17:00	116	0.10		10		0											
19:19:00	137	0.10		10		0											
19:22:00	127	0.03		10		0											
19:24:00	124	0.11		10		0											
19:26:00	133	0.11		10		0											
19:28:00	133	0.11		10		0											
19:30:00	137	0.11		10		0											
19:32:00	151	0.11		10		0											
19:34:00	168	0.11		12		0											
19:36:00	154	0.11		11		0											
19:38:00	166	0.12		13		0											
19:41:00	139	0.10		8		0											
19:43:00	132	0.12		12		0											
19:45:00	133	0.13		12		3	800								8		

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5	FFSSP Reference Volts = N/F	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9cc/s		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = NOT FITTED	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 3V	NOT FITTED	NOT FITTED

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B345

Date: 16/02/08	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 17:45:00	DAU1 Time: N/A	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
19:47:00	133	0.11		12		3	500								8		
19:49:00	148	0.11		12		3	800								8		
19:50:10	143	0.10		12		0.5	750								8	END R1	
19:51:53	154	0.12		12		1	700								8	START R1.1 @B 1000FT	
19:54:00	136	0.11		13		0.5	800								8		
19:56:00	143	0.13		13		0											
19:58:00	168	0.12		13		0											
20:00:00	161	0.13		14		4	600								8,3		
20:03:00	145	0.11		14		1	700								8		
20:05:00	181	0.11		13		0											
20:12:00	150	0.12		13		0											
20:20:00	131	0.11		7		0											
20:20:13	194	0.11		12		0										START P2	
20:22:00	102	0.10		8		0										FL030	
20:22:54	74	0.10		8		0										FL040	
20:23:54	43	0.09		2		0										FL050	
20:25:06	46	0.09		0		0										FL060	
20:26:12	35	0.11		0		0										FL070	
20:27:16	27	0.08		0		0										FL080	
20:28:15	20	0.09		0		0										FL090	
20:29:12	9	0.13		0		0										FL100	
20:30:00	30	0.09		0		0										FL110	
20:30:58	34	0.08		0		0										12000FT	
20:42:20	9	0.11		0		5										FL220	
20:46:40	1	0.01		0		0										FL240	
20:47:48	2	0.10		1		0										FL270	
21:02:32	6	0.07		0		0										END P2 FL340	
21:05:26	6	0.09		0		0										START R2 FL340	
21:09:00	3	0.09		0		0	NOISE									SONDE 1	
21:14:00	4	0.09		0		0										SONDE 2	
21:17:00	6	0.11		0		0										SONDE 3	
21:23:00	8	0.08		0		0										SONDE 4	
21:26:00	3	0.10		0		0	NOISE									SONDE 5	
21:33:57	13	0.08		0		0	NOISE									START R2.2	
21:37:00	8	0.07		0		0										SONDE 6	
21:40:00	12	0.06		0		0										SONDE 7	
21:43:00	13	0.07		0		0										SONDE 8	
21:56:36	17	0.07		0		0										START P3 FL340	
21:57:57	17	0.07		0		0										FL330	
21:59:00	28	00.07		1		0										FL320	
21:59:43	23	0.06		0		0										FL310	
22:00:28	25	0.07		1		0										FL300	
22:01:10	20	0.06		1		0											

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5	FFSSP Reference Volts = N/F	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9cc/s		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = NOT FITTED	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 3V	NOT FITTED	NOT FITTED

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B345

Date: 16/02/08	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 17:45:00	DAU1 Time: N/A	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: N/A	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
22:02:00	26	0.06		1		0										FL280	
22:02:30	28	0.06		1		0										FL270	
22:03:23	36	0.06		1		0										FL260	
22:04:08	106	0.05		2		0										FL250	
22:04:57	93	0.05		0		0										FL240	
22:05:59	59	0.06		0		0										FL230 PCASP SPECTRUM NOT GOOD	
22:06:45	31	0.05		0		0										FL220 PCASP SPECTRUM NOT GOOD	
22:07:32	26	0.05		0		0										FL210 PCASP SPECTRUM NOT GOOD	
22:08:21	24	0.05		0		0										FL200 PCASP SPECTRUM NOT GOOD	
22:09:09	24	0.06		1		0										FL190 PCASP SPECTRUM NOT GOOD	
22:09:57	32	0.09		1		0										FL180	
22:10:44	63	0.09		2		0										FL170	
22:13:09	43	0.07		0		0										FL140	
22:13:57	30	0.07		0		0										FL130	
22:14:56	47	0.08		0		0										FL120	
22:15:53	49	0.07		0		0										FL110	
22:17:36	47	0.08		2		0										FL090	
22:18:30	36	0.07		0		0										FL080	
22:19:30	32	0.07		0		0										FL070	
22:20:42	55	0.07		0		0										FL060	
22:21:51	68	0.09		1		0										FL050	
22:22:56	112	0.09		2		0										FL040	
22:24:05	126	0.10		2		0										FL030	
22:26:23	162	0.10		8		0										FL010 END P3 1000FT AGL	
22:27:49	130	0.10		8		0										START R3 @ POINT A 1000FT	
22:30:00	156	0.10		4		0											
22:32:00	149	0.11		8		0											
22:34:00	130	0.11		8		0											
22:36:00	163	0.11		10		0											
22:38:00	160	0.10		10		0											
22:40:00	149	0.10		10		0											
22:42:00	152	0.10		10		0											
22:44:00	126	0.10		9		0											
22:46:00	153	0.10		9		0											
22:48:00	130	0.10		6		0											
22:50:00	144	0.10		4		0											
22:52:00	140	0.11		2		0											
22:54:00	139	0.09		2		0											
22:56:00	174	0.11		20		0											
22:57:55	151	0.11		20		0										END RUN 3 (SHORT OF POINT B)	
22:58:54	178	0.12		10		0										START RUN 3.2 TOWARDS D	
23:00:00	132	0.11		8		0											
23:03:00	134	0.12		10		0											

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.5	FFSSP Reference Volts = N/F	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate = 0.9cc/s		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = NOT FITTED	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = 3V	NOT FITTED	NOT FITTED

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B345 1st sector **T/O:** 18:01:52
Date of flight: 16/02/08 **Land:** 23:17:37 (Barrow)

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		Not fitted
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b345_tas</p> <p>Start = 180200 End = 231700</p> <p>Time data processed to = 214618 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 1271</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = b345_tas Y = (X+1) = b345_tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B345 1st sector
Date of Flight: 16/02/08

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.9 180200 231700
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2d_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check.

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B345 2nd sector **T/O:** 01:42:56 on 17/02/08
Date of flight: 16/02/08 **Land:** 03:17:51

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		NOT FITTED
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B345 2nd sector****Date of Flight: 16/02/08**

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 164647
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 28450 Blocks written = 28450 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 014000 End = 032000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2dc good 2dp not operated Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 014000 End =032000 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 2dc 49 pages

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = 254000 End = 272000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 271847 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 27</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = Y = (X+1) B345_tas_2d2_pcas2</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B345 2nd sector
Date of Flight: 16/02/08 + 1

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Code updated to handle This flight Min size = Vol flow rate = 254000 272000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcas d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b345_tas_2d_pcas2 Y = X+1 = _tas_2d_pcas3
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check.

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B345	Date	16/02/2008	Operator	DHA	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
21:09:03	1	Launch	249.90 -51.20 15.06 227.70 28.20 -18.20 -154.127500 71.659600 10364.60
21:20:24	1	Land	1011.65 -21.16 73.13 208.07 4.58 -10.69 -153.870781 71.752466 562.55
			End drop time override 682.7 Surface alt unknown ticked
21:14:03	2	Launch	249.60 -50.90 13.21 218.20 28.40 -17.90 -154.089900 71.222800 10372.80
21:25:28	2	Land	1011.12 -22.57 56.57 242.82 4.32 -10.45 -153.840295 71.314792 562.48
			Surface alt unknown ticked
21:17:03	3	Launch	249.50 -51.50 13.78 219.30 33.00 -17.40 -154.070200 70.960400 10374.20
21:28:38	3	Land	1011.74 -20.88 64.74 271.31 5.00 -10.34 -153.835899 71.054160 544.28
			End drop time override 696.0 Surface alt unknown ticked
21:23:03	4	Launch	249.80 -52.90 15.80 217.60 30.80 -17.70 -154.030300 70.439800 10368.50
21:34:39	4	Land	1012.85 -23.75 72.36 250.11 2.60 -10.02 -153.814165 70.532314 529.56
			End drop time override 697.1 Surface alt unknown ticked
21:26:03	5	Launch	249.50 -52.60 14.63 225.20 32.40 -17.60 -154.061000 70.179800 10374.70
21:37:10	5	Land	1005.56 -21.83 77.04 20.42 1.47 -11.03 -153.851823 70.270172 564.18
			End drop time override 667.7 Surface alt unknown ticked
21:36:03	6	Launch	249.50 -52.40 13.52 240.50 26.10 -17.60 -153.116200 70.202200 10374.20
21:47:18	6	Land	1008.66 -22.50 75.19 139.99 0.95 -10.72 -152.894922 70.285032 538.97
			End drop time override 674.1 Surface alt unknown ticked
21:40:03	7	Launch	249.50 -53.40 13.79 227.50 23.80 -17.80 -153.486000 70.577800 10375.60
21:51:36	7	Land	1011.35 -22.89 68.73 248.99 1.42 -10.31 -153.270879 70.669321 531.54
			End drop time override 692.2 Surface alt unknown ticked
21:43:03	8	Launch	249.70 -53.70 13.13 223.50 24.70 -17.20 -153.785500 70.870000 10370.80
21:54:24	8	Land	1011.70 -22.58 57.64 265.32 2.85 -10.48 -153.565580 70.961262 537.36
			Surface alt unknown ticked
		Launch	
		Land	
		Launch	
		Land	
		Launch	
		Land	

WARNING - THERE IS A FAULT WITH THE RECORDED TELESCOPE POSITIONS, USE POSITION NOTED IN COMMENTS

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15:53:30.92 --- - - - -
15:53:30.92 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
15:53:30.93 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
15:53:30.93 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B345
15:53:30.93 --- - - - -
15:53:49.91 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:53:54.15 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:53:58.14 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
15:54:10.11 SWS - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:54:11.66 SWS - - - 600 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:54:15.77 USH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:54:17.88 USH - - - 600 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:54:21.24 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:54:22.79 LSH - - - 600 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
15:54:27.15 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:54:27.16 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:54:27.17 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:57:00.40 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
15:57:52.79 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
15:57:53.35 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
15:57:56.57 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
15:57:58.24 SWS 169.3 - - - - Telescope stopped.
15:58:01.52 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
15:58:03.18 SWS -0.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
15:58:06.80 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
15:58:08.46 SWS 170.2 - - - - Telescope stopped.
15:58:14.29 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
15:58:15.95 SWS -1.6 - - - - Telescope stopped.
15:58:27.84 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 118.956
15:58:29.50 SWS 119.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
16:18:11.27 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
16:18:16.82 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:18:17.14 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:18:17.18 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:18:23.26 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:18:23.58 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:18:23.79 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:19:04.60 SWS 175.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
16:20:03.12 --- - - - - *** CLPX-II Detachment to Fairbanks AK
17:01:42.48 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
17:01:49.53 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:01:49.56 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:01:50.24 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:01:55.97 LSH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:01:56.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:01:56.81 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:02:19.90 SWS 175.9 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
17:02:25.04 SWS 175.9 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
17:03:28.82 --- - - - -
17:03:28.82 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
17:03:28.82 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
17:03:28.82 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B345
17:03:28.82 --- - - - -
17:05:07.11 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
17:05:14.91 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
17:05:25.13 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 120.765
17:05:26.80 SWS 120.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
17:05:56.68 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:06:00.72 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:06:02.96 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:06:13.48 SWS - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
17:06:15.24 SWS - - - 600 - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
17:06:19.20 USH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.

```

17:06:20.75	USH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
17:06:24.30	LSH	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
17:06:26.02	LSH	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
17:06:30.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:06:30.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:06:30.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:06:38.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:38.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:38.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:38.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:06:39.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:06:39.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:06:44.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:06:44.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:06:45.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:06:46.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:06:51.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:58.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:07:01.78	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:07:08.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:15.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:07:20.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:27.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:07:31.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:37.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:07:41.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:47.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:31:19.68	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
17:31:23.00	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:31:33.56	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 121.522
17:31:51.76	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 92.270
17:32:00.55	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 124.515
17:32:06.85	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:32:13.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:13.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:13.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:19.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:32:19.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:32:19.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:33:34.43	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:33:39.43	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
17:33:52.73	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 116.570
17:47:41.96	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:47:49.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:47:49.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:47:50.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:47:55.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:47:56.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:47:56.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:49:30.43	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:49:39.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:39.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:39.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:45.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:49:45.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
17:49:46.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:03:46.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** t/o
18:36:21.54	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
18:36:28.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:36:28.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:36:28.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:36:34.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:36:35.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:36:35.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
18:36:38.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:36:38.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:36:38.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:36:45.49	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
18:41:10.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -9c

```

18:46:11.27 --- - - - - - *** Start P1 down from FL240
18:46:11.72 SWS 175.6 - - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
18:46:50.65 SWS 175.6 - - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
18:47:30.62 --- - - - - - *** Real start of P1
18:49:33.21 --- - - - - - *** some thin Ci at this level
18:54:39.26 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:54:39.28 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:54:39.75 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
18:54:45.74 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:54:45.95 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
18:54:46.22 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:04:51.72 SWS 175.6 - - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
19:05:32.15 SWS 175.6 - - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
19:06:27.51 --- - - - - - *** box temp -10c
19:09:51.67 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:09:51.69 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:09:51.90 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:09:58.36 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:09:58.41 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:09:58.66 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:15:03.80 --- - - - - - *** end profile start run at 1000'
19:15:27.60 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:15:27.61 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:15:27.69 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:15:34.14 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:15:34.45 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:15:34.75 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:25:35.76 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:25:35.90 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:25:36.32 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:25:42.23 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:25:42.43 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:25:42.77 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:29:23.97 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:29:24.00 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:29:24.14 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:29:24.80 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:29:30.62 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:29:30.83 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:29:31.29 LSH - - - - - Idling
19:32:17.04 --- - - - - - Reset shutters.
19:32:24.03 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:32:24.23 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:32:24.49 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:32:30.50 LSH - - - - - Idling
19:32:30.74 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:32:30.96 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:33:04.14 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:41:24.54 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:41:24.59 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:41:24.62 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:41:30.99 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:41:31.22 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:41:31.39 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:41:46.75 --- - - - - - *** box temp -10c
19:49:38.00 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:49:44.47 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:49:48.97 SWS - - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
19:49:48.98 SWS - - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
19:49:51.65 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:49:56.14 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:50:20.39 --- - - - - - *** End of Run 1.1
19:51:09.79 --- - - - - - ***
19:51:10.03 SWS - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:51:10.09 LSH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:51:10.12 USH - - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:51:14.52 SWS - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:51:16.73 LSH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:51:16.93 USH - - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

```

19:51:55.17 --- - - - - *** Start of Run 1.2
19:55:11.30 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:55:11.42 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:55:11.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:55:15.79 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:55:17.99 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:55:18.16 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:55:22.52 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
19:56:33.23 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
19:56:48.63 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:56:48.77 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:56:48.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
19:56:53.49 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:56:55.09 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
19:56:55.30 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:03:44.90 --- - - - - *** box temp -10c
20:04:29.05 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:04:29.21 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:04:29.33 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:04:33.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:04:35.50 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:04:35.72 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:04:38.29 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
20:05:54.12 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
20:08:13.84 --- - - - - ***
20:09:03.16 --- - - - - ***
20:10:26.69 --- - - - - *** Start of Run 1.3
20:19:38.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:19:38.61 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:19:39.01 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:19:42.92 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:19:45.11 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:19:45.47 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:20:14.65 --- - - - - *** start profile
20:22:50.76 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:22:51.10 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:22:51.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:22:55.26 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:22:57.60 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:22:57.82 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:23:05.59 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
20:23:05.60 SWS - - - 200 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
20:23:11.61 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:23:14.08 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:23:37.11 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
20:24:08.60 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
20:24:51.96 --- - - - - *** box temp -10c
20:39:46.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:39:47.21 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:39:47.25 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:39:49.33 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:39:53.69 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:39:53.90 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:40:00.84 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
20:40:00.85 LSH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
20:40:03.46 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:40:07.91 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:40:40.25 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
20:41:40.73 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
20:46:08.19 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:46:12.66 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:46:15.45 LSH - - 600 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
20:46:15.46 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
20:46:18.84 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:46:25.30 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
20:47:50.63 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:47:50.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:47:51.01 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
20:47:53.12 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

20:47:57.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:47:57.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:48:01.96	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
20:49:37.86	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
20:49:38.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
20:56:24.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:56:24.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:56:24.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:56:26.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:56:30.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:56:31.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:35.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:35.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:35.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:37.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:41.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:41.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:58.89	USH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
21:02:58.90	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
21:03:02.46	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
21:03:02.47	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 400ms.
21:03:06.29	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:03:10.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:03:10.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:03:10.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:03:12.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:03:15.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:03:15.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:03:37.17	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:05:38.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** Start of Run 2.1
21:16:05.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:16:05.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:16:05.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:16:08.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:16:10.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:16:10.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:22.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -9c
21:23:42.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:23:42.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:23:42.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:23:44.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:23:46.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:23:47.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:30:34.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:30:39.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:30:44.09	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
21:30:44.10	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
21:30:47.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:30:49.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:32:06.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** box temp -10c
21:33:39.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:33:39.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:33:39.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:33:42.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:33:42.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:33:44.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:33:57.51	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:33:58.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:35:10.67	SWS	175.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
21:35:11.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
21:35:21.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:35:21.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:35:21.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:35:24.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:35:24.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:35:26.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:35:30.31	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
21:35:30.34	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
21:35:32.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

```

21:35:34.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:45:57.97 --- - - - - *** box temp -10c
21:46:08.26 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:46:08.28 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:46:08.37 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:46:10.05 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:46:10.78 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:46:13.14 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:53:42.92 --- - - - - *** end of run 2. FL340
21:55:02.62 --- - - - - *** end run at 215408, not as suggested
above!!!!
21:56:39.36 --- - - - - *** start p
21:56:58.64 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
21:57:00.09 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
21:57:02.17 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
21:57:35.52 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
22:01:38.62 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:01:38.82 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:01:38.90 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:01:40.40 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:01:41.17 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:01:43.52 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:19:02.09 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:19:02.17 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:19:02.28 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:19:03.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:19:04.82 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:19:07.02 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:21:13.22 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:21:15.73 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:21:19.92 LSH - - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
22:21:19.93 LSH - - - 400 - NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
22:21:23.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:21:27.59 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:26:31.92 --- - - - - *** end p3
22:27:58.54 --- - - - - *** start run 3 1000'
22:36:03.81 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:36:04.03 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:36:04.06 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:36:05.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:36:08.54 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:36:08.78 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:36:12.48 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
22:36:33.29 --- - - - - *** box temp -10c
22:37:38.87 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
22:37:39.71 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:37:50.55 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:37:52.05 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:38:45.71 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:38:47.29 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:45:40.17 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:45:40.34 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:45:40.36 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:45:41.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:45:44.89 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:45:45.15 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:45:51.28 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
22:45:52.26 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
22:47:31.38 SWS 175.6 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
22:57:56.80 --- - - - - *** end run
22:58:08.45 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:58:08.75 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:58:08.80 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
22:58:10.01 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:58:13.23 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:58:13.46 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
22:59:01.69 --- - - - - *** start run
23:11:22.67 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
23:11:22.82 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

23:11:22.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
23:11:24.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:11:27.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:11:27.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
23:11:30.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
23:11:30.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
23:11:30.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
23:19:14.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.

1 min 120
2 min 240
3 min 360
4 min 480
5 min 600
6 min 720

ARIES flight log

Flight: BB45 page 1 of 3

Date: 16/2/08 Operator(s): CBS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CLAY-II FOXERANKS (AS) Type flask North of Barrow

Scans: either "[IGMs][co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

7640

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
1621	Grnd	1/120	HBB	clsd	70.84	71.86	Grnd cal
1623	Grnd	1/120	CBB	clsd	71.05	72.07	Grnd Cal
18337	FL240	1/120	HBB	clsd	70.61	72.94	
183426	FL240	120/1	HBB	clsd	70.85	72.88	
183551	FL240	120/1	CBB	clsd	71.06	72.12	
184156	FL240	Noise script		clsd	71.0	72.41	Noise script.
190514	FL84	cal script		clsd	70.81	72.75	CBB/HBB 1 min in all.
191448	1000'	cal script		clsd	70.92	72.15	" " script cal.
191641	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd	70.66	72.51	
19206	1000'	cal script		clsd	70.94	72.38	
192137	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd	70.62	72.62	
192517	1000'	1/60	HBB	clsd	70.84	71.68	Hot cal
192547	1000'	1/60	HBB	clsd	70.57	72.05	Cold cal
192628	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd	71.76	72.40	Noe over coast boundary
193000	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd	end 193050		Started 193050 after coast boundary
193106	1000'	cal					cal script
193238	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd	70.79	72.28	
193622	1000'	cal HBB					cal script
193744	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd			
194128	1000'	cal		clsd	70.86	72.21	cal script
194249	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd	71.07	72.30	Good structure
194623	1000'	cal		clsd			
194743	1000'	400/1	Noe	clsd	70.95	72.57	Good structure over ice breaks
1950	1000'	1/120	CBB		70.59	72.2	
195230	1000'	1/120	HBB		70.81	72.69	
195337	1000'	520/1	Noe	clsd	70.9	72.40	
195538	1000'	120/1	zen	clsd	70.85	71.68	
195655	1000'	cal			70.89	72.41	cal script
195804	1000'	520/1	Noe	clsd	70.85	73.12	
ARIES is 13 seconds Ahead							

1947200

ARIES flight log		Flight: B345	page 2 of 3
Date: 16/12/08	Operator(s): JASS	Res: 1	Gain A: 7 B: 2
Loc./Notes: CLP XII IASI			

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Sshtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
200237	R2	Cal CBB/HBB		Clso	7112	1189	
200403	R2	300/1	Nod	Clso			
200454	R2	120/1	Zen	open	7050	1195	
200609	R2	240/1	Nod	Clso			
200745							
201016				Cal script			
201740				Cal script			
201856		240/1	Nod	Clso	7071	1233	Around ground site ended 202026
201856	202021	Cal script		Clso	7118	1228	
210133	End P2	1/120		Clso	7074	1216	
210242	End P2	1/120		Clso	7059	1149	
210433	R	520/1	Nod	Clso	7083	1239	Run started @ 210542
210953		ARIES software hang					
121146		Keyboard ok					
		No housekeeping so rebooted ARIES as well.					
211626		Keyboard ok					
		CBB Temp set to 30					
211658	R2.1	Cal script		Clso	7580	3774	HBB set to 70
2118??	R2.1	520/1	Nod		7175	3408	Over pass from Satellite
212240		Cal script		Clso	7139	3065	
212427	R2.1	520/1	Nod	Clso	7071	3069	
212821		Cal script		Clso	7050	3063	
213205		Cal script		Clso	7080	3052	
213412	R2.2	120/1	Zen	open	7093	3014	
213521	R2.2	400/1	Nod	Clso	7070	2993	
213900	R2.2	Cal script		Clso	7073	3101	1.06 CBB/HBB
214027	R2.2	520/1	Nod	Clso	7057	3053	
214501	R2.2	Cal script		Clso	7092	3078	
214623	R2.2	520/1	Nod	Clso	7077	3137	
215053	R2.2	Cal script		Clso	7088	3073	
215209	R2.2	240/1	Nod	Clso	7072	2986	
215439		Cal script		Clso	7093	3073	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B345

page 3 of 3

Date: 16/2/08

Operator(s): CUSS

Res: 2

Gain A: 1 B: 1

Loc./Notes: CLP2-II 1st flight over sea ice

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
22626		HSB	Noise check				
227230	end P3	1/120	HSB	clsd	3000	71.13	
22745		1/120	CBB	clsd	70.91	30.22	
22758	R3-1	S20/1	Nov	clsd	70.82	30.39	
223407		cal script			71.05	30.59	
223623	R3-1	S20/1	Zen	open	70.48	30.55	Clear above.
223723		300/1	Nov	clsd	70.92	30.54	
22409	~	cal script			71.06	30.95	
22433	~	S20/1	Nov	clsd	70.64	30.64	
224601	~	cal script		clsd	70.93	30.72	
224722	~	S20/1	Nov	clsd	70.97	30.53	
225312	~	cal script		clsd	71.09	30.62	
225434	~	S20/1	Nov	clsd	70.65	30.69	end 225844
225838	end R3-1	cal script		clsd	70.04	30.25	
225922	start R3-2	S20/1	Nov	clsd	70.92	30.40	
227410	R3-2	cal script		clsd	70.81	30.28	
230660	R3-2	S20/1	Nov	clsd	70.91	30.16	
231119	R3-2 end	cal script		clsd	70.94	30.52	
							ARIES data 1/4 second ahead of DRS at end of flight.

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	16/02/08	Flight	B345	log pages
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CLPX-II		
Departure	Fairbanks		Arrival	Fairbanks		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on			at time	15:38		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	22	Ch	22	Ch18	19
Temperature controller set points		50°C	17	50°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	15:40		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	291.0	Cold	291.6		
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	15:41		
Scan indication		Monitor)	Visual		X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						X
Turn on Deimos CPU						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Start Deimos Software			at time	15:45		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	292.3	Cold	292.1		
Target heating						X
Scan indication		Monitor)	Visual		X
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} + ?$		at time	17:32		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.55	Cold	293.10	
	Deimos:	Hot	344.85	Cold	304.41	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	57.99	23.47	57.93	23.51		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	40.48	35.33	37.75	42.36	42.38	

Power changeover

Headset on before start		
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

CVI log

2/16/08 4:43:51 PM B345 16th Feb 2008 CLPX-II
2/16/08 6:16:26 PM Tip heater temp varying from about 2 to 30 on ground. Temp around 40 - 45 in flight.
2/16/08 6:17:02 PM PCASP dropped out on power change over.
2/16/08 6:25:42 PM Restart snoopy.vi
2/16/08 6:42:07 PM PC restart
2/16/08 6:43:08 PM lymann not responding to main vi, so re-zero. Success!
2/16/08 6:52:15 PM pcasp re started again, now working.
2/16/08 6:53:17 PM Just going through some cloud, readings of up to 6 on pcasp, readings on wing pcasp similer.
2/16/08 6:54:30 PM lymann hygro showing increased signal also cpc.
2/16/08 7:02:18 PM lpcasp coms are a bit dodgy! Keep loosing signal. Stops communicating. Needs adjustment with large hammer!
2/16/08 7:03:22 PM lymann hygrometer seems to be ok.
2/16/08 7:04:20 PM seatbelts on! profile decent to Barow
2/16/08 7:10:14 PM hygro showing signals around 0.1 to 0.2 so diluent turned down to zero.
2/16/08 7:15:49 PM pcasp working at the moment. hygro showing signal going up to 0.6 at 1000ft
2/16/08 7:16:12 PM Lots of snow!
2/16/08 7:20:12 PM Lots of snow!
2/16/08 7:25:47 PM pcasp signal a lot lower than cloud physics
2/16/08 7:30:55 PM over sea ice (not that you can tell by eye)
2/16/08 7:39:49 PM increase sample flow to 0.8 throught pcasp
2/16/08 7:41:56 PM hygro showing signal going bellow 0 - must be very dry!
2/16/08 7:49:55 PM end of run 1.1
2/16/08 7:51:41 PM start of run 1.2
2/16/08 8:01:51 PM just going into cloud, signal on hygro climb to 1.8
2/16/08 8:20:37 PM start of profile climb
2/16/08 9:03:27 PM end of profile climb 2
2/16/08 9:05:09 PM profile run at 340 dropping sonds
2/16/08 9:56:23 PM lyman zero
2/16/08 10:26:27 PM end of profile 3
2/16/08 10:27:37 PM start of run 3
2/16/08 10:28:36 PM dropped flow rate of pcasp
2/16/08 10:31:38 PM flow led has come back on on CPC
2/16/08 10:56:40 PM struggling to balance sheath flow and sample flow on PCSP - clean mirror flickering
2/16/08 10:57:47 PM end of run 3
2/16/08 11:23:49 PM land at barow and power down

Flight:

B345

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:	Not Fitted
Heimann:	OK
Deiced Temp:	OK
Non-deiced Temp:	OK

Hygrometers

FWVS:	OK
General Eastern:	OK
Johnson Williams:	OK
Nevezorov:	OK
Total Water Probe:	Minor Problems

Cameras

Downward Facing:	OK
Forward Facing:	OK
Rearward Facing:	OK
Upward Facing:	Fitted, Not Operated

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:	Fitted, Not Operated
GIN Applanix:	OK
INU Honeywell:	OK
Radar Altimeter:	OK
RVSM IAS:	OK
RVSM Static Pressure:	OK
XR5 GPS:	OK

Report Created 12/03/2008
15:06:34

Misc Core

AMTG:	OK
AVAPS:	OK
Cabin Pressure:	OK
Fax machine:	Fitted, Not Operated
Printer:	OK
S9 Static Pressure:	OK
Satcom C:	OK
Satcom H:	OK
Turb Centre-Static:	OK
Turb Left Right:	OK
Turb Up-Down:	OK
Turb Horizontal Chk:	OK
Turb Vertical Chk:	OK
Weather Radar:	Fitted, Not Operated

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:	OK
DLU BBR Lower:	OK
DLU BBR Upper:	OK
DLU Core Chem:	OK
DLU Core Consoles:	OK
DLU Port Aft:	OK
DLU Port Fwd:	Not Fitted
DLU Stbd Fwd:	Not Fitted

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:	Duff Data
BBR (IR) Lower:	OK
BBR (red) Lower:	Duff Data

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:	Duff Data
BBR (IR) Upper:	OK
BBR (red) Upper:	Duff Data

ARIES:	Minor Problems
DEIMOS:	Minor Problems
IR Camera:	Not Fitted
JNO2 Lower:	Not Fitted
JNO2 Upper:	Not Fitted
JO1D Lower:	Not Fitted
JO1D Upper:	Not Fitted
MARSS:	OK
SHIMS Lower:	OK
SHIMS Upper:	OK
SWS:	OK
TAFTS:	Not Fitted

Last Updated:

18/02/2008 19:18:30

Cloud Probes

2DC:	OK
2DP:	Duff Data
FFSSP:	Not Fitted
PCASP:	OK
2DS:	Not Fitted
ADA:	Not Fitted
CAPS:	Not Fitted
CCN:	Not Fitted
CDP:	Not Fitted
CIP 100:	Not Fitted
CIP 25:	Not Fitted
CPI:	Not Fitted
CVI:	Minor Problems
SID1:	OK
SID2:	Not Fitted

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:	OK
Filters 47mm:	Fitted, Not Operated
Filters 90mm:	Not Fitted
Neph - Dry:	OK
Neph - Wet:	OK
PSAP:	Fitted, Not Operated
AMS:	Not Fitted
CPC 3025 (AMS):	Not Fitted
INC:	Not Fitted
VACC:	Not Fitted
CPC 3010A (CVI):	OK

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:	OK
NOx TE42C:	OK
Ozone TE49C:	OK
Ozone TE49:	Not Fitted
SO2 TE43C:	Fitted, Not Operated
TDLAS (NIR) CH4:	Minor Problems
TDLAS (NIR) CO2:	OK
FAGE:	Not Fitted
Formaldehyde:	Not Fitted
NOx FAAM:	Not Fitted
NOxy:	Not Fitted
ORAC:	Not Fitted
PAN:	Not Fitted
PERCA:	Not Fitted
Peroxide:	Not Fitted
PTRMS:	Not Fitted
TDLAS (1C):	Not Fitted
WAS Bags:	Not Fitted
WAS Bottles:	Not Fitted

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:	Not Fitted
LIDAR:	Not Fitted
LTI:	Not Fitted
SAW Hygrometer:	Minor Problems

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B345

Date: 16 February 2008

Instruments

1. Zero Trap for Core Chem wet pre-flight. Ozone reading –12ppb during Zero. Allow to dry out.
2. IIU – T4 messages counting up on pre-flight. Reset IIU CB then okay.
3. HORACE Time Server – Not available pre-flight at SWS Rack
4. Video Tapes – none loaded in Video Recorder pre-flight.
5. HORACE / TWC – Constants not right on HORACE. Resurrect routine to produce best-fit constants from post-flight processing – Dave T.
6. DLUs – messages now counting as T2 (i.e. rather than T1), data looks okay on HORACE.
7. TWC – status light started flashing continuously on Profile at 1908 (TAT= -20C). All TWC paras 65535 DRSU. Reset TWC power, came up with status light flashing i.e. no start-up sequence. Possible intermittent connection to head? Switched off for ~10mins and switched on, no better, sw off. Tried again at 2025Z and status light came on and stayed on, checked CBs (now profiling up), 200V, phase B found to be popped out. Make CB then TWC starts up okay and working normally
Started flashing again in profile at 2224, again at TAT-20C, all channels at 65535DRSU. Switched it off. Phase B CB found to be popped again.
Okay on Barrow-F'banks leg until FL40 on descent, same problem.
8. 2DP – Usual cold (noise) problems at high level
9. MARSS display – problem with display when too many pcs viewing web page
10. Printer – not printing colours
11. Satcom Phone – no success in phoning ground-based Iridium phone from Satcom-H.
Received 2 calls from it inflight. Will try calling it from a landline later
12. UBBRs – Clear & Red signals on HORACE don't look right. Red higher than Clear till well into flight.
13. ARIES – crashed during high level run
14. DEIMOS hot target heater overwhelmed most of time. MARSS quick-look data jibberish but processed data looks okay.
15. SWS – good
16. Core Chem – Ozone up to 400ppb (stratospheric air)
17. AVAPS – 8 good sondes (2 slow with GPS). New receive
18. CVI – PCASP signal low, FWVS good.

TWC Zero level = 2046 DRSU

Aircraft

1. Cabin very warm at start

ISDN Emails

Nil connections

Satcom-H Calls

DFL Ops normal x 1

Issues – Cabin very warm at start (to keep galley & toilet water from freezing). Got to 29C at back of aircraft so cooled it down.

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

el

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 16/2/08

Flight No: B 345

Pre-Flighter: *Woolley*

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	<i>Done</i>
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	<i>NO SIGNAL IN HANGAR</i>
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	<i>Done</i>
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	<i>Done</i>
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & on AUTO	<i>SOBS</i>
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input type="checkbox"/>			
25	<input type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	<i>SOB</i>
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	<i>NOB</i>

No.	√ or x	Location	Action	Comments
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
<u>External Checks</u>				
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	<i>SOB</i>
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	<i>SOB</i>
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol!**
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
<input type="checkbox"/>		Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
<input type="checkbox"/>		ICEX applied		
<input type="checkbox"/>		Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
<input type="checkbox"/>		Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

Flight B345 19:30:06

Heading 348 deg Speed 197 knots Height 1.1kft Press 973mb

Lat 70°48.0'N Long 154°24.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 231 deg

Temp -20.83C Dewpoint -20.97C

From 18:36:04 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	973.19	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-20.84	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-20.97	deg C
++++	DEW POINT (FLUORESCENCE WVS)	-23.46	deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B345:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as any PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	01 Apr 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras
4 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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